

Cobalt(III) complexes of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$: Synthesis, spectral characterization and redox behaviour

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Abstract : Six new cobalt(III) complexes of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$, where R = H, Me, Et, *t*-Bu, COMe and CN have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, UV-Vis, FT-IR and ^1H NMR spectral techniques. The results of the spectral studies revealed that these complexes possess a $cis\text{-}\beta$ arrangement of ligands around the metal ion. Molar conductance measurements supported the 1 : 2 nature of these complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicated that the complexes were diamagnetic. Thermal studies revealed that these complexes are thermally stable up to 115 °C. The redox potential values obtained from differential pulse voltammetric technique of these complexes indicated that the redox behaviour depends on the nature of the sixth ligand.

Keywords : Cobalt(III) complexes, pyridines, electrochemical and spectral studies.

Introduction

During the past few decades, the study of cobalt complexes gained considerable interest due to their wide range of applications¹⁻⁷. In continuation of our earlier report on the synthesis, spectral characterization and electrochemical behaviour of some cobalt(III) complexes⁸ of the type $cis\text{-}\beta\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{RC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$, in this article we report the synthesis, spectral characterization and redox properties of similar complexes containing 4-substituted pyridine as one of the ligand. Although the synthesis of $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(\text{pyridine})\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ ion has been reported earlier⁹, no attempt was made with substituted pyridines as one of the ligands along with trien and chloride ion. Such an attempt will definitely help to study the structural effects due to the nature of the sixth ligand on the reactivity/properties of these types of complexes.

Experimental

Materials and methods : All chemicals used were of commercially available reagent grade. Triethylenetetramine (trien) was distilled before use. 4-Substituted pyridines were purchased from Aldrich, India and were used as received. Double distilled water was used for recording differential pulse voltammetry and conductance measurements. Elemental analysis, TGA, FT-IR, electronic, ^1H NMR spectra were recorded to characterize the complexes⁸. The electrochemical experiments were

performed using differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) technique as reported earlier⁸.

Synthesis of Co^{III} complexes : The Co^{III} complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ (where R = H, Me, Et, *t*-Bu, COMe and CN) were prepared from $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}^{10}$. In a typical experiment, acid free $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (3.2 mmol) was suspended in water (2 ml) and was ground in a mortar with dropwise addition of the 4-substituted pyridine (3.2 mmol) for nearly 0.5–2 h. Calculated amounts of liquid of substituted pyridines were added directly while solid pyridines were dissolved in 2 ml alcohol and added. After the addition was completed, the mixture was set aside (~0.5 h) until no further change in colour was noticed. The resultant paste was rinsed with alcohol and ether over a Buckner funnel and was recrystallized twice in acetone-DMF mixture.

Results and discussion

The physical and analytical data of the Co^{III} complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{trien})(4\text{-R-Py})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$ (where R = H, Me, Et, *t*-Bu, COMe and CN) are given in Table 1. All the Co^{III} complexes gave satisfactory elemental analysis (C, H, N) confirming to the general composition. The complexes are all diamagnetic as expected. The molar conductance values (Table 1) in water (298 K) identify the species as 1 : 2 electrolytes¹¹.

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the Co^{III} complexes

R ^a	Colour	Elemental analyses (%) :			Molar conductance (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)
		Found (Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	
None	Violet	34.12	6.11	16.35	144
		(33.93)	(5.91)	(17.99)	
4-Me	Violet	34.67	5.79	16.85	160
		(35.73)	(6.20)	(17.36)	
4-Et	Blue	39.01	5.92	16.34	101
		(37.41)	(6.47)	(16.78)	
4- <i>t</i> -Bu	Violet	41.12	6.08	17.97	157
		(40.44)	(6.96)	(15.73)	
4-COMe	Blue	35.95	6.07	17.56	187
		(36.19)	(5.80)	(16.24)	
4-CN	Blue	34.27	5.52	20.94	177
		(34.78)	(5.31)	(20.28)	

^aSubstituent in Py moiety.

Electronic spectra : A representative electronic spectrum recorded in water is shown in Fig. 1. The absorption maxima and molar extinction coefficients of the Co^{III}

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of [Co(trien)(Py)Cl]Cl₂ in aqueous solution.

complexes are reported in Table 2. Regular octahedral Co^{III}L₆³⁺ complexes have two UV-Vis spin allowed transitions, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$. In tetragonal complexes of the type Co^{III}L₄X₂, the first band is splitted into two, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_{1g}$ at low energy and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ at higher energy. In *trans* complexes this splitting is sufficient to completely resolve this band into two components, which is rarely the case in *cis* complexes. Further, ϵ in *cis* com-

Table 2. Electronic spectral data for the Co^{III} complexes

R ^a	${}^1A_g \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ nm (log ϵ) ^b	Charge transfer nm (log ϵ) ^b
None	505 (1.96)	366 (1.95)
4-Me	513 (2.12)	363 (2.07)
4-Et	518 (2.13)	369 (2.10)
4- <i>t</i> -Bu	504 (2.14)	363 (2.10)
4-COMe	504 (2.10)	365 (2.05)
4-CN	502 (2.08)	364 (2.01)

^aSubstituent in Py moiety, ^b ϵ_{\max} in M⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

plexes are much greater than the corresponding *trans* values¹². In the present study, all the Co^{III} complexes show two absorption bands. The absorption bands at ca. 360 nm of the complexes were assigned to the MLCT band, while the bands at ca. 500 nm were assigned to the first absorption band i.e. due to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transition. The observed positions and intensities strongly suggest a *cis* rather than a *trans* structure for these complexes¹². Further, the electronic spectrum of these complexes were found to resemble that for *cis*- β -[Co(trien)Cl₂]⁺ ion¹³ and *cis*- β -[Co(trien)(RC₆H₄NH₂)Cl]²⁺ ion⁸ suggesting that these complexes also possess a *cis*- β arrangement of ligands around the Co^{III} ion. Furthermore, the positions of these bands vary very little through the series of complexes, thus indicating that the ligand field about the cobalt ion remains almost constant.

Infrared spectra : The FT-IR bands characteristics of these complexes only were considered and they are presented in Table 3. In all the Co^{III} complexes studied the N-H stretching region occurs in the range of 3107-3207 cm⁻¹ which is characteristic of *cis*- β -isomer (2985-3330 cm⁻¹)¹⁴. The bands \sim 1600 cm⁻¹ may be due to the anti-symmetric NH₂ bending vibrations. It is well established that the peaks in the 1290-1335 cm⁻¹ region is due to the symmetric NH₂ deformation¹⁵. Thus, in the present study, the bands due to NH₂ deformation observed in the 1295-1311 cm⁻¹ region confirmed that the structure of the cobalt(III) complexes is similar to that of *cis*- β -[Co(trien)X₂]²⁺ ion¹⁴ and *cis*- β -[Co(trien)(RC₆H₄NH₂)Cl]²⁺ ion⁸ proposed earlier. A new band observed in the FT-IR spectra of the Co^{III} complexes in the 545-576 cm⁻¹ region may be attributed to the M-N stretching¹⁵ and the band observed in the region of 1500-1600 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to heterocyclic ring vibration¹⁶.

Table 3. FT-IR spectral data of the Co^{III} complexes^a

R ^b	N-H stretching	NH ₂ bending	NH ₂ deformation	CH ₂ bending	CH ₂ wagging	CH ₂ rocking	M-N stretching
None	3121s	1589s	1304m	1448s	1304sh	911m	545s
4-Me	3107m	1585s	1305m	1439s	1305sh	899w	553m
4-Et	3207s	1580s	1311m	1442s	1311sh	914m	574s
4- <i>t</i> -Bu	3112s	1562s	1305m	1443s	1305sh	872m	576m
4-COMe	3192s	1594m	1295m	1440s	-	-	569s
4-CN	3198s	1566m	1295w	1447s	1295sh	927w	554m

^aIn cm⁻¹, ^bsubstituent in Py moiety.

¹H NMR spectra : A representative ¹H NMR spectra recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ is shown in Fig. 2. It is evident from the spectra that, (i) a signal centered at ~3.33 ppm belong to the center ethylene linkage of the trien ligand. The remaining center ring protons, as well as the protons in the terminal ethylene linkages, may overlap to form the complex multiplet centered at approximately 2.88 ppm¹⁷. The signals around 2.88 ppm confirmed that the Co^{III} complexes exist as *cis*-β isomers rather than *cis*-α ones¹⁸. (ii) The resonance peaks in the 6.2–7.2 ppm range may be assigned to the protons in the Py ring¹⁹. The downfield shift occurs with the *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-protons of the pyridine ring appearing at 8.9, 7.6, 7.9

ppm in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the [Co(trien)-(Py)Cl]Cl₂ complex, corresponding to 8.50, 6.99, 7.36 ppm in the free ligand as expected due to coordination of the pyridine nitrogen to the metal ion²⁰.

Thermal analysis : Thermal investigation of a representative complex, [Co(trien)(Py)Cl]Cl₂, was made in the temperature interval from room temperature to 800 °C in stream of nitrogen. The Co^{III} complex decomposed in a four stage process as shown by the presence of four breaks in the TGA graph²¹. The complex was found to be thermally stable up to 115 °C as the TGA plateau shows barring the removal of moisture from the complex. Above 115 °C a rapid decomposition occurs with a mass loss

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of *cis*-β-[Co(trien)(Py)Cl]Cl₂.

corresponding to the loss of two chlorine atoms present outside the coordination sphere (Stage 1). The loss of masses of about 29% and 10% for stages II and III respectively are recorded and are accounted by the loss of trien ligand in two stages. The procedural decomposition temperature for stage IV is close to 556 °C and the decomposition ends at 798 °C. Mass loss of 21% accounts for the loss of the pyridine moiety into volatile matter leaving the final residue.

Electro-reduction study : As the waves of cyclic voltammetric study of the Co^{III} complexes are poorly defined²², differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) technique was used to study the redox behavior of these complexes. The redox potential data for all the complexes in water is given in Table 4. The voltammogram of all these complexes exhibited a reversible cathodic and anodic peak in

L = 4-R-Py (where R = H, Me, Et, *t*-Bu, COMe or CN)

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Table 4. Electrochemical data from dPV for the Co^{III} complexes in water

R ^a	E _{pc} (V) (III/II)	E _{pa} (V) (II/III)	E _{1/2} (V)	ΔE _p
H	-0.053	-0.163	-0.108	110
4-Me	-0.168	-0.240	-0.204	72
4-Et	-0.176	-0.280	-0.228	104
4- <i>t</i> -Bu	-0.164	-0.256	-0.210	92
4-COMe	-0.140	-0.231	-0.185	91
4-CN	-0.080	-0.144	-0.112	64

^aSubstituent in Py moiety.

the -0.1 to -0.2 V range which is probably be due to Co^{III}/Co^{II} couple. The separation between the anodic and cathodic peak potentials (ΔE_p) values showed the quasi-reversible nature of the Co^{III}/Co^{II} redox couple²³. The results indicated that the E_{1/2} values depend on the nature of the sixth ligand however the experimental data failed to confirm to the usual Hammett or its modified equations²⁴.

Conclusion : Six new Co^{III} complexes were prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, UV-Vis, FT-IR, and ¹H NMR spectral techniques. Based on the foregoing spectral results, the following structure has been proposed for the [Co(trien)(4-R-Py)Cl]Cl₂ complexes with *cis*-β configuration. Magnetic susceptibility values indicated that these complexes are diamagnetic and conductance studies revealed that they are all 1 : 2 electrolytes.

Note

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